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Novel Ceramic fibre - Zirconium diboride composites for solar receivers in concentrating solar power systems

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Abstract

Ultra-high temperature ceramic matrix composites, UHTCMCs, are a new class of composites which combine boride phases with carbon fibres to achieve new structural and functional properties and were originally designed for aerospace applications. For the first time, this work investigates the optical response of UHTCMCs in view of their possible application as high temperature solar absorbers in Concentrating Solar Power systems. Carbon fibre-reinforced ZrB₂ pellets with different fibre type and arrangement were manufactured and characterized from the point of view of optical properties and surface microstructure. The composites had high fractions of ZrB₂ (~40 vol%) and carbon fibres (up to 55 vol%). Spectral hemispherical reflectance in the range 0.3-16 μm wavelength was assessed and compared to pure boride and graphite phases. The solar absorptance significantly increased with respect to the pure boride, reaching or even overpassing the solar absorptance of silicon carbide. Thermal emittance, calculated from 800 K to 1500 K temperature, increased as well in comparison to the pure boride, but always remained lower than that of SiC. These optical properties, combined with structural damage tolerance and light weight, suggest that UHTCMCs are of great interest as high temperature solar absorbers, overpassing the weaknesses of current solar receivers, as well as those of the most promising alternative materials to date.

Keywords: UHTCMCs; carbon fibre; concentrated solar power; emittance; ZrB₂

1. Introduction

Changes in energy production and management are urged by a global rising concern with environmental preservation, promoting the quest of new approaches and multifunctional materials for sustainable energy harvesting. The energy coming from sun is clean, safe and cost-effective. Concentrating Solar Power (CSP) technology is one of the several methods to collect and convert solar radiation into electricity. CSP plants work based on a simple principle whereby a mirror system concentrates the rays of the sun into a receiver, generating elevated temperatures there. A pipe is run through at this point, through which a fluid with the ability to take heat from the receiver flows before passing through a heat exchanger, so that the sunlight-generated heat can produce either industrial steam or electricity by running a turbine. Solar tower plants are representative examples of CSP technology, with currently achieved operating temperatures below 600 °C, to comply with molten salts thermal energy storage [1]. However, motivations are recently emerging to drive the research towards the increasing of CSP operating temperature, like the need to boost the efficiency of thermodynamic cycles for power generation, which increases with operating temperature. In addition, thermal applications have been recently proposed in the so-called Concentrating Solar Thermal, CST. Two of such high-temperatures examples can be found in the green production of hydrogen [2] and sustainable aviation fuels (SAF) [3], which, driving endothermic reactions at high temperatures through solar heat, are able to produce fuels from water and CO₂ and thus to effectively

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close the fossil fuel carbon cycle [4], but which require temperatures from above 700 °C up to ~1550 °C. These solar-driven chemical processes show an outstanding potential. For instance, they are thought to be able to supply the whole global demand of jet fuels [5] or hydrogen [6], thus significantly decreasing both the global dependence from fossil fuels and the greenhouse emissions.

The solar absorber element is one of the main bottlenecks for CSP temperature increasing [7–9]. Spectrally-selective coatings deposited on specific substrates can be used at low temperatures, but at high temperatures they are no more reliable and alternative strategies must be considered, such as the use of proper bulk solar absorber materials able to conjugate high temperature resistance and favourable thermophysical and optical properties.

Ultra-High Temperature Ceramics (UHTCs) include borides, carbides and nitrides of group IV and V and are characterized by the highest melting points exceeding 3000 °C, elevated temperature strength like 600 MPa and 800 MPa above 1500 °C [10], oxidation resistance [11] and other peculiar properties such as high thermal (80 – 110 W/m·K up to 2000 °C), and electrical conductivity [12]. This combination of excellent properties makes them the election materials for extreme applications. They were mainly investigated in the literature for military and aerospace applications [13], but some authors of the present work have proposed [14] and extensively studied their use for solar applications in the recent past. We proved promising properties such as the low thermal emittance and high spectral selectivity, identifying the relevant parameters and best strategies to optimize them [15,16]. However, for the actual use in CSP of bulk sintered UHTCs, further open issues have to be addressed, like material's damage tolerance and thermal shock resistance to withstand thermal gradients without suffering premature failure. To this aim, new fibre-reinforced UHTCs have been designed and produced, by incorporating reinforcing phases, such as C or SiC fibres into UHTC matrices [10]. This new class of developed materials has the ability to combine the oxidation resistance of UHTCs phases with the damage tolerance of fibres. Composites of this type have been widely studied and developed during the H2020 EU-funded project C3harve (Next Generation Ceramic Composites for Harsh Environment and Space [17]). Properties have been characterized at room and elevated temperature demonstrating the high potential of these composites. Moreover, oxidation studies and arc jet tests in a plasma wind tunnel facilities demonstrated an excellent stability up to 2100 °C [18,19].

The present work, for the first time, investigates the optical response of Ultra-High Temperature Ceramic Matrix Composites (UHTCMCs) with the purpose to assess their properties as novel solar absorbers able to overcome the limits of conventional UHTCs. The type of composite investigated here featured a ZrB₂-based matrix with a few amounts of secondary SiC phases and a carbon fibre (Cf) content around 50 – 60 vol%. With the aim of screening the most interesting surface textures, we considered different fibre configurations and porosities. In fact, it is well known that surface porosity, resulting in a roughness increase, largely affected the optical response [15]. Possible advantages in combining UHTC phases with carbon fibres are illustrated in Fig. 1. With a suitable design, the addition of carbon fibres may improve the optical properties, especially the absorbance and emittance, may impart damage tolerance, machinability and lightness. On the other hand, UHTC phases, besides being intrinsically solar selective, protect the carbon fibres from oxidation. A sketch summarizing the mutual benefits arising from this combination are illustrated in Fig. 1.

The optical properties of fibre-reinforced ZrB₂ composites were compared with those of reference ZrB₂ bulk ceramics, to understand how the presence of carbon fibres and surface preparation affect optical absorbance, reflectance and emittance. Playing with surface roughness and textures, different surface patterns were prepared to evaluate the influence of fibre orientation/fibre amount/porosity and roughness on the optical properties. SiC- and graphite based materials were also considered for reference.

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Fig. 1. Concept for development of novel receivers based on Cf reinforced UHTCs

2. Experimental

2.1. Sample Preparation.

Commercial starting materials were used for the production of UHTCMCs: ZrB_2 (Grade B, H.C. Starck, Germany, particle size range 0.5 - 6 μm , impurities (wt%): 0.2 C, 1.3 O, 0.19 N, 0.1 Fe, 1.4 Hf); α -SiC (Grade UF-25, H.C. Starck, Germany, D50 0.45 μm); PAN-derived carbon fibres (T800HB-6000, TORAYCA, Japan), diameter 5 μm , coating: pyrolytic carbon (PyC) 0.0811 g/m (coating thickness \sim 0.5 μm); pitch-based carbon fibres (XN80-6K, Granoc, Japan), diameter 10 μm , uncoated [20].

ZrB_2 - SiC powder mixtures were prepared by ball-milling in ethanol, dried by rotary evaporator and sieved. Then, a water-based slurry was prepared according to previous studies [21] and used to impregnate the carbon fibre cloths: unidirectional (UD) and plain woven (2D) cloths. Infiltrated cloths were cut and stacked in 0/90° configuration following the same alignment of fibre among layers to realize green pellets, see Fig. 2 for more details.

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Fig. 2. Sketch of stacking of UD and 2D carbon fibre cloths to realize UHTCMCs.

Green samples were consolidated by hot pressing using an induction-heating furnace (MP 20(II), SIATEM, Ing. Allaria Alto Vuoto, Italy) in the range 1800 °C – 1900 °C according to previous studies [21].

Five surface patterns were analysed to evaluate the influence of fibre orientation, their amount, sample porosity and surface roughness on the optical properties. Samples were prepared cutting the composites to expose either the fibre cross section or the longitudinal section (see Fig. 3), as follows:

-Polished_C exposed pitch-based carbon fibre cross sections, visible as elliptical dark spots and were obtained from composites with 0/90° architecture, after a 45° cut. This sample was polished down to 1 micron to obtain as smooth a surface as possible.

-Polished_L exposed PAN-based carbon fibre longitudinal sections, visible as long dark filaments, obtained from a 0/90° composite, polished with the same procedure;

-Polished_W exposed criss-crossed pitch-based carbon fibres obtained from a polished 2D composite, with the same procedure above.

For longitudinal section types of surfaces, two more variants with different roughness were considered:

-Porous_L exposed longitudinal PAN-based carbon fibre sections, obtained from unidirectional samples with 0/90° architecture, with a 20% of porosity.

-Rough_L exposed pitch-based carbon fibres in the longitudinal direction after a scratching procedure to increase the surface roughness.

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Fig. 3. Sketch of sample exposed surfaces with the fibre arrangement: a) represents the case of **Polished-C** sample, b) represents longitudinal cuts, as in **Polished_L**, **Porous_L** and **Rough_L** samples; c) sketches the configuration of **Polished_W**.

For the sake of comparison, optical properties of fibre-free reference samples were also reported, see Table 1: ZBM10 [15] was a polished ZrB_2 -based sample with a relative density of $\sim 96\%$; ZBM10P [15] had the same composition but a relative density of $\sim 87\%$ and was polished as well. SiC (Ra = 0.3) [22] was a monolithic SiC-based sample with a relative density $> 99\%$ and SiC(Ra0.7) [14] was a monolithic SiC-based reference sample with a relative density of $\sim 88\%$. Moreover, the following reference samples were prepared and analysed: a porous graphite with a relative density of 81% machined from a commercial material (Grade 2020, Mersen, Italy), a fully dense polished graphite with a dense mirror-like surface, supplied by Graftech. Finally, a pitch-based fibre unidirectional preform was prepared to expose raw fibres.

2.2 Characterization of surface morphology.

Bulk densities were determined by the Archimede's method or by weight-to-volume ratio; theoretical densities were deduced using the rule of mixtures on the basis of nominal compositions. Residual porosity, ρ , was determined either by mercury porosimetry (MIP) in the 0.0058-100 μm range (Pascal 140 and Pascal 240 series, Thermo Finnigan, U.S.A.) or by image analysis on scanning electron microscopy pictures of polished sections (Image-Pro Plus® Analyzer 7.0, Media Cybernetics, U.S.A.). The relative density, ρ , was deduced as $(1-p)$, where p indicates the porosity fraction. Sections for microscopy were prepared polishing them down to a 0.25 μm finish with a semi-automatic polishing machine (Tegramin-25, Struers, Italy).

Microstructures of as-sintered and polished surfaces were analysed using a field emission gun-scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM, ZEISS Sigma, Carl Zeiss Microscopy GmbH, Germany). Moreover, identification of secondary phases was carried out by X-ray micro-analyser (EDS, INCA Energy 300, Oxford instruments, UK). Surfaces exposed for the optical characterization were also analysed by a digital microscope (RH-2000, Hirox Europe, France).

The mean surface roughness (Ra) of samples surfaces was measured using a commercial contact stylus instrument (Taylor Hobson mod. Talysurf Plus) fitted with a 2 μm -radius conical diamond tip over a track length of 8 mm. Four linear scans in different directions were collected for each sample and the values were averaged.

2.3 Optical properties analysis

Hemispherical reflectance spectra were acquired using a double-beam spectrophotometer (Lambda900 by Perkin Elmer) with Spectralon®-coated integration sphere for the 0.25-2.5 μm wavelength region and a Fourier Transform spectrophotometer (FT-IR "Excalibur" by Bio-Rad) with gold-coated integrating sphere and liquid nitrogen-cooled detector for the range 2.5-16.0 μm .

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From experimental reflectance data ($R^{\cap}(\lambda)$), the spectral absorbance $\alpha(\lambda)$ or emittance $\varepsilon(\lambda)$ of these fully opaque materials can be obtained, as:

$$\alpha(\lambda) = 1 - R^{\cap}(\lambda) = \varepsilon(\lambda) \quad (1)$$

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Microstructure and properties of UHTCMC samples

Compositions, densities, fibre volumetric content (FVC) and roughness data are summarized in Table 1. Typical microstructural features have been already described in previous papers [10,23]. The composites contained about 50-60 vol% of carbon fibres and they had a relative density higher than 90%, with exception of the **porous-L** samples, with about 20% of residual porosity, see Table 1. As for the fibres, we analysed composites with both PAN- and pitch-based carbon fibres. For the sake of clarity, PAN-based fibres with diameter $\phi \sim 5 \mu\text{m}$ have a turbostratic structure and were coated with a 400 nm Pyrolytic carbon coating (PyC) to limit excessive reaction at the interface. Pitch-based carbon fibres, $\phi \sim 10 \mu\text{m}$, are characterized by a higher degree of graphitization, a typical onion-like structure and were used uncoated. For dense composites, the fibre/matrix interface was quite strong, due to reaction with the matrix during sintering. In the case of samples with PAN-based carbon fibres, the coating favoured the formation of weaker interfaces [10]. Since, only surfaces are relevant for the optical characterization, they were analysed in detail as described below.

Table 1. Microstructural features and solar absorbance of C/ZrB₂, bulk ZrB₂ and SiC samples.

Sample	Reference	FT*	FVC, TP*	Morphology of exposed fibres	AEF*	Surface preparation	P*	Ra*	α^*
			(%)		(%)		(%)	(μm)	
Polished-C	This work	0/90	~50, Pitch	Cross sect., 45° cut	~50	Polished	~9	0.3±0.1	0.73
Polished-L	This work	0/90	~55, PAN	Longitudinal	~34	Polished	~9	0.4±0.2	0.78
Polished-W	This work	2D	~58, Pitch	Fibre cross weave	~34	Polished	~9	0.6±0.1	0.76
Porous-L	This work	0/0	~55, PAN	Longitudinal	n.a	Grinded	~19	2.0±0.7	0.85
Rough-L	This work	0/90	~50, Pitch	Longitudinal	n.a	Scratched	~9	4.4±2	0.84
ZBM10	[15]	-	-	-	-	Polished	~4	(25±2)·10 ⁻³	0.48
ZBM10P(porous)	[15]	-	-	-	-	Polished	~13	1.18±0.07	0.71
SiC(Ra0.3)	[22]	-	-	-	-	Electrodischarge	<1	0.7±0.1	0.76
SiC(Ra0.7) (porous)	[14]	-	-	-	-	Electrodischarge	10	0.3±0.1	0.77
Porous Graphite	[24]	-	-	-	-	Grinded	9	n.a	n.a
Polished Graphite	[25]	-	-	-	-	As supplied	<1	n.a	n.a
Pristine Fibers	[20]	-	-	-	-	As-supplied	n.a	n.a	n.a

*Acronyms: fibre texture (FT); fibre volume content (FVC) and type of precursor (TP); amount of exposed fibres (AEF); residual bulk porosity (P); parameter Ra of surface roughness (Ra), spectral absorbance (α).

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Fig. 4. SEM images of the surface of samples at different magnification: a-c) **Polished_C**, d-f) **Polished_L**, g-i) **Polished_W**, j-l) **Porous_L** and m-o) **Rough_L**.

Polished_C – Features of this sample are shown in Fig. 4a-c, taken from a polished cross section. Fibres appeared as black spots and were homogeneously distributed in the white contrasting ZrB_2 matrix, Fig. 4a,b. In the matrix, a little amount of porosity can be recognized. Fig. 4c shows details of the matrix/fibre interface and secondary phases like SiC and C residues. After polishing, the amount of fibres on the surface did not change with respect to the starting material, because fibres and matrix resulted grinded in similar way.

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Polished_L –Micrographs in Fig. 4d-f show the regular distribution of fibre longitudinal sections, at different magnification, interspaced with matrix grains. Despite the polishing procedure, the surface finish appeared quite coarse. Further details evidence that some graphite from the coating had spread to surrounding areas, Fig. 4f. Image analysis indicates an average fibre volume content (FVC) of 34.2 ± 8.8 vol%.

Polished_W – This sample showed a macroscopic texture, Fig. 4g-i, with some inhomogeneities such as the presence of cracked matrix-rich areas surrounded by fibre-rich areas with a criss-cross pattern. At higher magnification, it can be noticed that fibres were highly damaged (Fig. 4h). This could also be due to the peculiar onion like structure of the pitch-based carbon fibres. The fibre/matrix interface was very strong in these composites; therefore, fibres were rather exfoliated than completely removed. Damaged fibres are well visible also in Fig. 4g. For the dense samples, roughness measurements led to similar values, with a slight increase from **C** to **L** to **W** type samples.

Porous_L – This sample was characterized by a higher content of open porosity in the bulk (Fig. 34j-l). Thanks to the lubricant action of graphite from the PyC coating, the surface appeared quite smooth, despite the internal matrix porosity. It is likely that some graphite was spread over the surface (Fig. 4k), as previously observed for sample **Polished-L** with PyC-coated PAN-based carbon fibres, see Fig. 4e. The roughness was higher than previous dense samples, around 2 μm .

Rough_L – In this case, the microstructure was a dense one, with pitch-based carbon fibres. The surface was heavily scratched to remove the most surficial layer. This operation caused a strong damage, with fibres which were often torn from the matrix. Consequently, the surface had a roughness of 4.4 μm , e.g. similar to that of the porous material. Due to this, the fibre surface concentration appeared to be lower, even if an exact estimation was difficult due to the surface irregularities. Despite the different porosity levels, 9 and 19%, respectively, the matrices of these two last samples appeared equally granular, see Fig. 4k,n.

Optical 3D images and plotted profile measurements of the surface of **Polished_L**, **Porous_L** and **Rough_L** samples are reported in Fig. 5. Pictures are consistent with the roughness data.

Dense **Polished_L** sample resulted mainly flat but some voids (surface profile was found in a range of 2 μm), created by fibre removal during polishing, are visible (Fig. 5a). **Porous_L** and **Rough_L** samples, see Fig. 5b and Fig. 5c respectively, are corrugated, with surface profile found in ranges of 8 and 18 μm . **Rough_L** is more corrugated of **Porous_L** and it is interesting to note that this feature is clearly more pronounced across fibre direction. The preferential removal of fibres during grinding created this surface textures.

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Fig. 5. Surface Topography obtained by optical 3D images of the surface of samples: a) **Polished_L**, b) **Porous_L** and c) **Rough_L**.

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3.2 Optical properties of UHTCMC receivers and reference materials.

Fig. 6: Hemispherical reflectance spectra of polished samples. Image on the right is a magnification of the inset.

Fig. 6 shows the hemispherical reflectance spectra of polished fibre-reinforced samples, together with the spectrum of a reference dense and polished ZrB_2 [26]. In Fig. 6 it is also shown the spectrum of a polished graphite sample (PADLEX) to allow recognizing the carbon contribution to the overall spectra of fibre-added borides. The addition of carbon-fibres dramatically decreased the reflectance curves of ZrB_2 ceramics on the whole considered range with respect to the reference pure boride. The plot on the right in Fig.6 is an enlargement of the 0.3-3 μm spectral range and allows identifying the spectral signatures of graphite (dip around 380 – 460 nm) and ZrB_2 (shoulder around 1.3 μm) and how they combine into the fibre-reinforced samples. While the graphite dip can be seen in all the composite samples, the ZrB_2 feature is kept only by **Polished_W**, while graphite, whose curve shows an opposite concavity in that spectral range, practically compensates completely the ZrB_2 concavity for **Polished_C** and **Polished_L** samples.

Considering the fibre-reinforced specimens, **Polished_L** and **Polished_C** show similar curves, only slightly differing each other for wavelengths lower than 5 μm and with a lower reflectance of **Polished_L**. It is interesting to notice that 5 μm also corresponds to the diameter of the fibres used in **Polished_L** sample and longitudinally exposed on the surface. We could infer that the lower reflectance of **Polished-L** in this range could be ascribed to a selective absorption of wavelengths lower than 5 μm due to trapping effects at the graphite-boride interface. The reflectance of the **Polished_W** sample is superimposed to that of **Polished_L** below 2 μm wavelength, due to similar roughness values of the two samples, while it remains significantly lower than that of any other sample going deeper into the infrared. This happens even if **Polished_W** shows a surface percentage of exposed fibres similar to **Polished_L** and lower than **Polished_C**, as shown in Table 1. This brings us to attribute the low infrared reflectance of **Polished_W** (~10% difference in the absolute reflectance values from ~6 μm on) to the presence of cracked matrix-rich areas, shown in Fig. 7. All the three fibre-containing samples show a small spectral feature at around 12 μm which confirms the presence of SiC, about 5 vol% according to microstructural analysis.

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Fig. 7: Optical image of a detail on the surface of **Polished-W**, showing the massive presence of cracks in a matrix-rich area.

Fig. 8: Hemispherical reflectance spectra of unpolished samples. Image on the right is a magnification of the inset.

If unpolished samples are concerned, Fig. 8, the fibre-added pellets are compared with a 13% porosity, 1.2 μm roughness, 2- μm pore size ZrB_2 sample [15,27] and to both unpolished porous graphite and pristine carbon fibres. Again, the effect of carbon fibres is to significantly decrease the reflectance curve with respect to the pure boride. The graphite dip in the UV-blue is shown by all composites. Traces of SiC are detected in these samples as well (spectral feature around 12 μm). Despite the roughness of sample **Rough_L**, 4.4 μm , was higher than **Porous_L**, about 2 μm , the absorbance was lower, which is an unexpected outcome. In previous reports, for instance, increasing the roughness resulted in an increase in the absorbance [15]. In the present work, however, scratching operations on the surface of **Rough-L** led to partial removal of the black highly-absorbing fibres. Therefore, we believe that the real surface density of fibres in the **Rough_L** sample was lower than the nominal composition and this led to a higher reflectance compared to **Porous_L** even with a twice as high roughness.

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From experimental spectra, it is possible to calculate some parameters useful to evaluate the potential of the materials as sunlight absorbers in solar receivers for thermodynamic solar plants, namely the solar absorptance α , the total hemispherical emittance ε at the temperature T , and the spectral selectivity α/ε , as follows:

$$\alpha = \frac{\int_{0.3\mu m}^{3\mu m} \alpha(\lambda) \cdot S(\lambda) d\lambda}{\int_{0.3\mu m}^{3\mu m} S(\lambda) d\lambda} \quad (2)$$

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\int_{0.3\mu m}^{16.0\mu m} \varepsilon(\lambda) \cdot B(\lambda, T) d\lambda}{\int_{0.3\mu m}^{16.0\mu m} B(\lambda, T) d\lambda} \quad (3)$$

where $S(\lambda)$ is the sunlight spectral distribution [28] and $B(\lambda, T)$ is the blackbody spectral radiance at the temperature T . For a more complete evaluation, the emittance in Eq. 3 has been calculated at different temperatures from 800 K to 1500 K. As a methodology comment referred to these parameters, it should be observed that the values calculated from Eqs. 1-3, being obtained from room-temperature spectra, represent an estimation widely used in the literature for a comparative evaluation among materials, while they cannot represent exact values in operative conditions, which would need the knowledge of the spectra at the considered temperature, and result generally underestimated [29].

The calculated α values are listed in the last column of Table 1. For a more comprehensive evaluation, we also took into account, as a comparison material, silicon carbide (SiC), which is considered the most advanced high-temperature solar receiver material employed in existing plants to date. Therefore, in Table 1, we also included the data of two previously investigated SiC ceramics (a dense and a 12% porosity one) [29,30].

For an ideal solar absorber, α should be the nearest as possible to unity, to maximize the solar energy harvesting. From the values shown in Table 1, the carbon-fibre-loaded samples appear superior to pure ZrB_2 ceramics, including the porous version. In addition, they are fully comparable or even better than SiC, whose major force point for solar receiver applications is considered its high solar absorptance itself.

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Fig. 9. Calculated thermal emittance as a function of temperature. Left: polished samples; Right: Unpolished samples.

Fig. 9 shows the temperature-dependent thermal emittance calculated from Eq. 3 for the fibre-reinforced samples and reference ZrB_2 and SiC materials. Thermal emittance quantifies unavoidable radiative energy losses of a body at temperature T, and thus it should be kept as lowest as possible to maximize the amount of solar energy made available for exploitation. The obtained emittance results confirm that both polished and unpolished specimens are promising for solar receiver applications, showing in all cases lower emittance than SiC at all temperatures.

3.3 Discussion – Preliminary design of carbon fibre – UHTC receiver

Although preliminary, this analysis allowed us to already screen the best solutions amongst those presented and attempt a first design of the novel solar receiver materials.

Optical characterization: Data on absorbance and emittance suggest that the best surface arrangement was that of **Polished_C** sample, with exposed fibre cross sections, homogeneously dispersed in a fully dense matrix and with a proper surface finishing. The total amount of fibres varied from 35 to 55 vol% in the surface and did not significantly affect the optical response. An increase of roughness or porosity led to a tangible advantage in absorbance but was accompanied by an increase of emittance. As illustrated before, for all the fibre reinforced composites, absorbance highly improved compared to pure ZrB_2 and emittance was always lower than SiC based materials. Hence, the addition of fibre led to a significant advantage compared to both bulk ceramics.

Thermal conductivity: This property is important because the solar absorber should transfer heat to another carrier medium. ZrB_2 ceramics enriched with carbon fibres are good thermal conductors, due to the high conductivity of the constituent phases. Monolithic ZrB_2 has a conductivity of 60 W/(m·K) [31] up to about 1500 °C. Carbon fibres have extremely high thermal conductivity along the axis (320 W/(m·K), given from the supplier) and much lower conductivities in the transverse direction (5-10 W/(m·K)). Thermal conductivities (K_{th}) of these composites are of course highly anisotropic, being affected by the fibre arrangement. As many other properties, K_{th} is also affected by the presence of porosity that is a non-conductive phase. Therefore, although all the composites were good conductors along some direction, experimentally measured thermal conductivities were quite different. We measured **Polished_C** and **Porous_L**, as representative of antipodal situations. The fibre arrangement in **Polished_C** was the most favourable for heat transmission from the exposed surface to the bottom and indeed thermal conductivity reached ~140 W/(m·K) at room temperature, with a slight decrease to ~100 W/(m·K) at 1000 °C [23]. On the contrary, the fibre positioning of **Porous_L** was the most unfavourable and K_{th} was much lower, 11 W/(m·K), at room temperature to about 20 W/(m·K) at 1500 °C [10]. In this case, the property was negatively affected by the low transverse conductivity of carbon fibres and, likely, by porosity within the matrix. Finally, SiC is also a very good thermal conductor, with conductivity ranging from 125.6 W/(m·K), at room temperature [32] to about 20 W/(m·K) at 1500 °C (unpublished results).

Mechanical properties/oxidation resistance: From this point of view, type of fibre, FVC, fibre/matrix interface and matrix density are the most important factors affecting the mechanical response. Again, two examples are represented by **Polished_C** and **Porous_L**. Mechanic response of these two composites was investigated in a previous work [33] and it was found that although mechanical response was satisfactory for both types of composites, the oxidation/ablation resistance was much better for samples with structure similar to **Polished_C**. In this case, in fact, the high density of the matrix was more effective in protecting the fibre from environmental attack.

Compared with bulk dense ZrB_2 and SiC ceramics, carbon-fibre loaded ZrB_2 samples offer several advantages thanks to an improved toughness, damage tolerance and thermal shock

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resistance. Fracture toughness ranges from 3 to 5 MPa·m^{0.5} for bulk ceramics, with a catastrophic failure, whilst increases to 10 –20 MPa·m^{0.5} for UHTCMCs depending on the fibre disposal [10].

Moreover, the excellent mechanical properties are kept even at temperature up to 1800 °C [34].

Specific weight. Elevated densities of UHTC phases (ZrB₂ density: 6.1 g/cm³, HfC density: 12.2 g/cm³) could be a major disadvantage in engineering applications. Addition of carbon fibres (density about 1.7-2.2 g/cm³) is the most efficient way to reduce weight. Composites of the present work have specific weight almost halved compared to the bulk ZrB₂, e.g. around 3.5 g/cm³, just slightly above SiC density, 3.2 g/cm³.

Table 2 compares the materials analysed in this work, indicating the level of accomplishment of selected criteria that are considered important for CSP application, including functional, environmental and mechanical properties. This very preliminary analysis confirmed the good performance of UHTCMCs and amongst them, the best combination identified was the sample labelled as **Polished_C**.

Table 2. Comparison of various material in comparison with desired requirements. Numbers from 1 to 5 express the level of accomplishment of requirements in the first column (1 means fairly accomplished, 5 means fully accomplished)

Desired features of receivers	Polished_C	Polished_L	Polished_W	Rough_L	Porous_L	SiC100	ZBM10
High Absorbance >0.5	4	4	4	5	5	5	3
Low Emittance <0.5	4	4	3	2	2	3	5
Thermal conductivity, from surface to bottom >20 W/(m·K) @ 1500 °C	5	4	4	3	3	4	5
High Damage tolerance/ thermal shock resistance	5	5	5	5	5	2	2
High oxidation resistance	5	5	5	3	3	5	5
Refractoriness	5	5	5	5	5	4	5
Moderate density, <3.5 g/cm ³	5	5	5	5	5	5	2

4. Conclusions

In this work ZrB₂ ceramic samples reinforced with carbon fibres have been manufactured and systematically investigated from point of view of microstructural and optical properties for solar absorbing materials in high-temperature thermodynamic solar plants.

The method of slurry impregnation and sintering was selected to realize both dense and porous samples. This method allowed achieving composites with high fractions of ZrB₂ phase and high carbon fibre fraction.

The introduction of carbon fibres dramatically changed the samples optical properties with respect to the pure boride. In particular, solar absorptance was consistently increased, overcoming thus what is considered the main weakness of Ultra-High Temperature Ceramics (UHTCs) and reaching or even overpassing the solar absorptance of silicon carbide, which is the most advanced high-temperature solar absorber material to date. Thermal emittance, albeit increased in comparison to the pure boride, remained lower than that of SiC, definitely proving the high potential of these carbon-fibres reinforced borides for solar absorbers applications.

In summary, outstanding optical properties, high mechanical strength even at elevated

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temperature, damage tolerance, thermal shock resistance and light weight favourably candidate fibre-reinforced Ultra-High Temperature Ceramic composites for a new concept of ultra-high-temperature solar absorber material.

5. Acknowledgements

E.S. wishes to thank Mr. M. D’Uva and Mr. M. Pucci (CNR-INO) for technical assistance.

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